

TYPOMORPHOLOGY OF TRADITIONAL SETTLEMENTS IN THE FRENCH RIVIERA METROPOLITAN AREA

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SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

The goal of the present research note is to characterize the traditional settlements of the metropolitan area of the French Riviera and to study their spatial distribution within the study area. This will be done through the development of an appropriate typology of traditional settlements, as they could be observed during the 19th century. The typology will then be applied to the 80 settlements of the study area, which will be listed and characterized individually. This work is a direct contribution to WP3 of the emc2 project, aiming at studying the historical formation of linear settlements within the metropolitan areas covered by the emc2 project.

The case study of the present note is the metropolitan area of the French Riviera, around the coastal cities of Cannes, Antibes, Nice, Monaco and Menton. This area corresponds to the coastal and pericoastal sections of the Alpes-Maritimes Department in France and is bordered by two administrative and two natural boundaries. To the west lies the Var Department, and to the east, Italy. While to the south there is the Mediterranean sea, the northern boundary corresponds to a discontinuity in the topography, dividing the hilly and pre-alpine coastline from the alpine hinterland. Stretching 65 km along a SW-NE axis, the study area extends up to 30 km inland. According to INSEE, the 73 municipalities involved comprised more than 1.1 million inhabitants in 2021, which is 96% of the Department's population. Adding to these 73 municipalities, the enclave of the Principality of Monaco hosts 36 000 inhabitants. Since our aim is to understand traditional structures before all the demographic and urban transformations of the 20th century, the study period corresponds mainly to the 19th century. This is the period preceding rural exodus and the mass motorization of the inhabitants, which started after WW2. By traditional settlement, we mean any sufficiently large aggregation of buildings to develop a specific form (at least 20-30 buildings are required, the difference within this threshold depending on the building size). This is especially the case with old towns, but also with village centers, faubourgs, and hamlets. Some hilly areas, namely around Nice, Menton and Grasse, were also concerned by dispersed rural dwellings, which didn't give rise to any form of aggregated settlement.

The French Riviera is known to be characterized by the presence of many compact hilltop villages (Reclus 1864, Raybaud et Chiappello 2020). One of the objectives of our work was thus to understand weather linear settlements, which are the focus of the emc2 project, played any role in structuring early urbanization in the study area. For this, a specific typology of settlement forms was developed, distinguishing linear structures, simple-shaped surface-like structures and complex-shaped surface-like structures (Figure 1, the 10 morphotypes). This typology was confronted with the empirical data, namely 19th century cadastral maps of settlements in the study area. This confrontation, helped confirm the proposed typology and sometimes improve it, by adding new specific forms (namely the V-linear form and the assemblages).

From the very beginning, it was assumed that the site's topography played an important role in shaping the form of traditional settlements. Four categories of sites were defined: plain or valley (1), hill-flank degrading towards a waterbody (2), hill- or mountain-flank (3), and ridge, promontory, or hilltop (4).

Five different data sources were employed:

- The old French cadastral maps. It will be remarked that the Var River constitutes a politico-historical separation of the study area, with cadastral maps created between 1809 and 1835 to the west, and those produced between 1862 and 1875 to the east, after the annexation of the County of Nice to France.
- Recent orthophotographs (2012-2023) available thanks to Google satellites.
- The buildings layer from the BD TOPO of IGN (15/12/2023), which is a vector layer of the digital footprint of each building in 2D in the form of polygons. Attribute data provides the date of appearance (DATE_APP) for 38% of the buildings: "Date of creation, construction, or appearance of the object, or the earliest date at which its presence on the ground can be attested," according to the MAJIC files and data from the DGFIP.
- The named streets layer from the BD TOPO of IGN (15/12/2023), which is a vector layer of the digital footprint of each street in 2D in the form of polylines.
- The 3D view of the current state of the area when available on Google Earth.

The old cadastral maps were the main source to characterize each settlement according to our typology. The main features of each settlement, allowing this characterization were then manually entered in a GIS project, as it will be explained in what follows. Within cadastral maps, settlement and building footprints were mainly evaluated at the level of the “tableaux d’assemblage”, which are maps at a scale of 1:10,000. Sometimes, it was needed to verify some building footprints in cadastral sectional plans, which are detailed maps at a scale of 1:2,000 (and sometimes even more). For a given year, each municipality corresponds to a single “tableau d’assemblage”, except for Nice, which has seven.

On each cadastral map, the village core is identified. If no clear identifiable structure existed in the 19th century data, a diachronic comparison is made with more recent cadastral maps (1900 – 1950). Once the traditional formation is located, a comparison is made with recent images (2D and 3D). This allows for an assessment of the nature of the site and the evolution of the urban structure, confirming or not the previously identified morphotype. Then, within the GIS project, buildings from before 1900 are displayed in red, buildings from after 1900 in gray, and current buildings in white. This representation corresponds to the permanence of built-up elements, i.e. buildings that have survived to the present day. Differences are then observed between the buildings present on the old cadastral maps and those still present today, most often replaced by more recent buildings or simply destroyed without replacement.

Still within the GIS, the built permanence is superimposed with the street system. Main features of each settlement are manually digitized in the GIS, according to settlement type. Within linear settlements, the main streets are thus identified. They generally concentrate a higher density and compactness of both the old and current buildings, organize more or less perpendicular secondary streets (which are normally shorter) and host specific main buildings (church, city hall, etc.) with or without forecourt or a little square in front. Additionally, there is a consistent orientation of the roofs that are perpendicular to the main streets, as already observed by Caniggia and Maffei (1979). In ring settlement, the main ring is identified, as an organizing circular street (other main axes could be present within it). As for the other surface-like settlements, only the perimeter of the built-up surface is identified and digitized within the GIS project.

Manual modeling of the shape of structures in GIS is more or less straightforward. In the case of well-defined old villages or towns, modeling is not problematic. However, smaller settlements are more subject to interpretation (Bendejun, Blausasc, Cantaron, Châteauneuf-Villevieille, Saint-Blaise). Moreover, diffuse urban areas present centers that appeared late (Pégomas, Le Rouret) or centers without an obvious structure (Mandelieu-la-Napoule, Roquefort-les-Pins). Another difficulty lies in the length of linear structures. Linear structures are extended as long as the density and compactness of the old buildings are sufficient. The old cadastral maps show more evident boundaries where the buildings stop, unlike the current buildings. Consequently, when a significant discontinuity in the buildings is noted, beyond 50 meters, the linear structure is interrupted.

A specific case is the one of the assemblage structures, characterizing many old towns (with overgrowth of faubourgs) and some of the most complex villages. For them, we tried to identify the different components of the assemblage, as well as the form of the original core, allowing to re-attribute them to a basic form.

Table 1 lists the settlements according to their identified morphotype. Figure 2 maps the settlements using icons of conventional dimension to represent the simplest forms, but keeping their main orientation in space. A detailed catalogue describes each of the 80 settlements in alphabetical order.

References

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Figure 1 – The 10 Morphotypes

10 MORPHOTYPES		Valley / Plain	Flank to Waterbody	Flank	Ridge Hill-Top
1 Axe 		Saint-André-de-la-Roche	Cap d'Ail	Touët-de-l'Escarène	Castagniers
2-parallel Axes //		La Trinité	Villeneuve-Loubet	Le Tignet	La Roquette-sur-Var
2-convergent Axes v			Théoule-sur-Mer	Le Bar-sur-Loup	Contes
3 Axes Y		La Colle-sur-Loup	Roquebrune-Cap-Martin	La Roquette-sur-Siagne	Cagnes-sur-Mer
4 Axes Y		Le Rouret		Spéracèdes	
Ring				Vence*	Aspremont
Pinecone			Villefranche-sur-Mer	Peille	Berre-les-Alpes
Grid		Mouans-Sartoux	Saint-Laurent-du-Var	Valbonne	Castellar
Large Complex Surface (LCS)		Sospel	Antibes	Grasse*	Menton*
Assemblage*		Vallauris	Nice Centre	Saint-Jeannet	Tourrettes-sur-Loup

Table 1 - OVERVIEW OF THE 80 SETTLEMENTS

LINEAR SETTLEMENTS		43 (+1)
1-axis I	18 (+1)	
Beausoleil Cantaron Cap d'Ail Castagniers Castillon (New village 1950s) Chateauneuf-Villevieille Colomars Cros-de-Cagnes (Cagnes-sur-Mer) Nice Barri de Masson / Magnan	Nice Sainte-Hélène Pégomas Peymeinade faubourg Roquefort-les-Pins Saint-André-de-la-Roche Saint-Blaise Saint-Jean-Cap-Ferrat Touët-de-l'Escarène Tourrettes-Levens	
2-parallel axes //	4	
La Roquette-sur-Var Le Tignet	La Trinité Villeneuve-Loubet	
2-convergent axes V	3	
Le Bar-sur-Loup Contes	Théoule-sur-Mer	
3-axes Y	16	
Beaulieu-sur-Mer Bendejun Blausasc Cagnes-sur-Mer Le Cannet Châteauneuf-Grasse La Colle-sur-Loup L'Escarène	La Gaude Mandelieu-la-Napoule Nice Carras Roquebrune-Cap-Martin La Roquette-sur-Siagne Saint-Agnès Saint-Cézaire-sur-Siagne Saint-Martin-du-Var	
4-axes X	2	
Le Rouret	Spéracèdes	
SURFACE-LIKE SETTLEMENTS		23 (+8)
Ring	10 (+2)	
Aspremont Castillon (Old village) Falicon Gattières Gorbio	Monaco Mougins Opio Peillon Saint-Paul-de-Vence	

Pinecone

9 (+5)

Auribeau-sur-Siagne
Berre-les-Alpes
Le Broc
Cabris
Carros

Èze
Peille
Peymeinade centre
Villefranche-sur-Mer

Grid

4 (+1)

Castellar
Mouans-Sartoux

Saint-Laurent-du-Var
Valbonne

COMPLEX-SHAPED SETTLEMENTS

14 (+3)

Complex Large Surface

2 (+3)

Antibes

Sospel

Assemblage

12

Linear-based (1):

Drap

Grid-based (1):

Vallauris

Ring-based (2):

Cannes

Vence

Pinecone-based (5):

Biot

Tourrettes-sur-Loup

Levens

La Turbie

Saint-Jeannet

Complex-surface-based (3):

Grasse

Nice centre

Menton

Figure 2 - OVERVIEW MAP

Main findings

Linear settlements are an important feature of traditional urbanization in the Alpes-Maritimes. They account for more than half of the traditional settlements, including linear villages and faubourgs. One-axis structures and three-axis Y structures are the most frequent. Coastal faubourgs (in Nice, Cannes, Cagnes-sur-Mer, Menton) are typically built around one axis, although Carras, in Nice, is Y-shaped. Many simple one-axis linear structures, and the few two-parallel-axes structures, are built on hill flanks (with or without access to a waterbody), but single-axis settlements can also be found on ridges (like Colomars). Ridge and hilltop sites favour both V and Y-shaped linear structures, ring structures, and pinecone structures. The latter are very specific to the French and Italian Riviera and consist of a few parallel streets following the contour lines of a hilltop or promontory, without forming a closed ring, and connected by several irregularly disposed small streets. Grid-based structures are typically planned (like the bastide towns of Valbonne and Mouans-Sartoux) and situated on the plain or on gently sloped flanks.

The most articulated linear settlement is Drap, which consists of an assemblage of the original Y structure of the medieval village with a particularly long linear structure along the western bank of the Paillon River, which is a 19th-century faubourg. Particularly interesting structures also characterize Vallauris (an original medieval bastide grid connected by a linear structure to a later 18th-century grid) and Vence (an original medieval ring structure complemented by a very small grid extension and several linear faubourgs). The city of Nice presents the most outstanding assemblage: a late medieval complex-surface core (the old town), surrounded by a first grid extension to the south (18th century), two grid extensions to the east and west (19th century), and three linear extensions beyond them: northeast, north, and west, along the coast. The latter is just the beginning of a series of linear extensions (Magan, Saint-Hélène, Carras), which still showed some interruptions in the 1870s.

Catalogue legend

ANTIBES

Large Complex Surface (LCS)

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1814

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

ASPREMONT

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1865

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

AURIBEAU-SUR-SIAGNE

Pinecone

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1810

Old cadastral map 1847

Old cadastral map 1933

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LE BAR-SUR-LOUP

2-Axes V

Flank

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

BEAULIEU-SUR-MER

3-Axes Y

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1873

Old cadastral map 1934

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

BEAUSOLEIL

1-Axis I

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1874

Old cadastral map 1976

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

BENDEJUN

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1933

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

BERRE-LES-ALPES

Pinecone

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

BIOT

Assemblage: CLS, pinecone and two 1-axis I

CLS-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1813

Old cadastral map 1978

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LE BROC

Pinecone

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1835

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CABRIS

Pinecone

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1819

Old cadastral map 1834

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CAGNES-SUR-MER

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1834

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CANNES

Assemblage: ring and 1-axis I / coastal settlement

Ring-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1813

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LE CANNET

3-Axes Y

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1813

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CANTARON

1-Axis I

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1867

Old cadastral map 1944

Orthophotography 2019

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CAP D'AIL

1-Axis I

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1874

Old cadastral map 1909

Old cadastral map 1934

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CARROS

Pinecone

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CASTAGNIERS

1-Axis I

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1865

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CASTELLAR

Grid

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1863

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CASTILLON (New village 1950s)

1-Axis (winding)

Flank

Old cadastral map 1934

Old cadastral map 1974

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CHÂTEAUNEUF-GRASSE

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

1-Axis I

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA COLLE-SUR-LOUP

3-Axes Y

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1834

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

COLOMARS

1-Axis

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1875

Old cadastral map 1935

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CONTES

2-Axes V

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

CROS DE CAGNES (Cagnes-sur-Mer)

1-Axis

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1834

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

DRAP

Assemblage: 3-Axes Y and 1-axis I

3-Axes-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

L'ESCARÈNE

3-Axes Y

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1867

Old cadastral map 1935

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

ÈZE

Pinecone

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1873

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

FALICON

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1870

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

GATTIÈRES

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA GAUDE

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1834

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

GORBIO

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1862

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

GRASSE

Assemblage: CLS and two 1-axis I

CLS-based: Flank

Old cadastral map 1809

Old cadastral map 1973

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LEVENS

Assemblage: Pinecone and 1-axis I

Pinecone-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1864

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

MANDELIEU-LA-NAPOULE

3-Axes Y

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1809

Old cadastral map 1967

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

MENTON

Assemblage: CLS and two 1-axis I

CLS-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1862

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

MONACO (Principality of)

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Military staff map (1820-1866)

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

MOUANS-SARTOUX

Grid

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1813

Old cadastral map 1980

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

MOUGINS

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1862

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

NICE BARRI DE MASSON / MAGNAN

1-Axis

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1872

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

NICE CARRAS

3-axes Y

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1872

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

NICE CENTRE

Assemblage: CLS, four 1-Axis I and three grid

CLS-based: Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1873

Old cadastral map 1873

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

NICE SAINTE-HÉLÈNE

1-Axis I

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1872

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

OPIO

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Old cadastral map 1938

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

PÉGOMAS

1-Axis

Flank

Old cadastral map 1809

Old cadastral map 1847

Old cadastral map 1934

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

PEILLE

Pinecone

Flank

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

PEILLON

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1866

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

PEYMEINADE CENTRE

Pinecone

Flank

Old cadastral map 1868

Old cadastral map 1943

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

PEYMEINADE FAUBOURG

1-Axis

Flank

Old cadastral map 1868

Old cadastral map 1943

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

ROQUEBRUNE-CAP-MARTIN

3-Axes Y

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1862

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

ROQUEFORT-LES-PINS

1-Axis I

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1833

Old cadastral map 1974

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA ROQUETTE-SUR-SIAGNE

3-Axes Y

Flank

Old cadastral map 1813

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA ROQUETTE-SUR-VAR

2-Axes //

Flank

Old cadastral map 1864

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LE ROURET

4-Axes X

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1833

Old cadastral map 1934

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-ANDRÉ-DE-LA-ROCHE

1-Axis I

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1872

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-BLAISE

1-Axis I

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1864

Old cadastral map 1864

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-CÉZAIRE-SUR-SIAGNE

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1819

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-JEAN-CAP-FERRAT

1-Axis I

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1873

Old cadastral map 1935

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-JEANNET

Assemblage: Pinecone and two 1-Axis I

Pinecone-based: Flank

Old cadastral map 1833

Old cadastral map 1935

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-LAURENT-DU-VAR

Grid

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1813

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-MARTIN-DU-VAR

3-Axes Y

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1864

Old cadastral map 1933

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINT-PAUL-DE-VENCE

Ring

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2014

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SAINTE-AGNÈS

3-Axes Y

Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1863

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

Complex Large Surface (CLS)

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1864

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

SPÉRACÈDES

4-Axes X

Flank

Old cadastral map 1819

Old cadastral map 1933

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

THÉOULE-SUR-MER

2-Axes V

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1826

Old cadastral map 1974

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LE TIGNET

2-Axes //

Flank

Old cadastral map 1819

Old cadastral map 1848

Orthophotography 2012

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

TOUËT-DE-L'ESCARÈNE

1-Axis I

Flank

Old cadastral map 1867

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

TOURRETTE-LEVENS

Assemblage: 1-Axis I

1-Axis-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1864

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

TOURRETTES-SUR-LOUP

Assemblage: Pinecone and two 1-Axis I

Pinecone-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1833

Old cadastral map 1853

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA TRINITÉ

2-Axes //

Valley / Plain

Old cadastral map 1872

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

LA TURBIE

Assemblage: Pinecone and 3-Axes I settlements

Pinecone-based: Ridge Hill-Top

Old cadastral map 1874

Old cadastral map 1959

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

VALBONNE

Grid

Flank

Old cadastral map 1813

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

VALLAURIS

Assemblage: 2 Grid and 1-Axis I

Grid-based: Flank

Old cadastral map 1813

Old cadastral map 1874

Orthophotography 2022

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

VENCE

Assemblage: Ring, grid and 4-Axes I

Ring-based: Flank

Old cadastral map 1834

Old cadastral map 1942

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

VILLEFRANCHE-SUR-MER

Pinecone

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1873

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

VILLENEUVE-LOUBET

2-Axes //

Flank to Waterbody

Old cadastral map 1833

Orthophotography 2023

Remnants of old built-up from 2023

Typomorphology of Traditional Settlements in the French Riviera Metropolitan Area

Research Note - D3.1b
emc2 Project WP3

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